

PROBLEMS FACED BY PRIMARY SCHOOL TUTORS IN ACTIVITY BASED LEARNING (ABL) IN CUDDALORE DISTRICT

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Abstract:

Education in India was through the Gurukul system up to a few centuries ago till the beginning of British rule in India. But in this Activity Based Learning (ABL) method transaction to the primary schools, tutors faced lot of problems. So the vestigator has identified the tutors working in the primary schools situated in cuddalore district as sample. Hence, the researcher has made an attempt to study the problems faced in activity based learning of the primary school tutors. The objectives of this study is to find study the level of Difficulties faced by primary school teaches in Activity Based Learning and the significance of the difference between the following of sub-samples with respect to their problems faced in Activity Based leering. The following tool has been used for collecting data. Problems faced in ABL scale standardized by K. Muruganatham (2010). It is taken from the school register. The tool was administered to a random sample of 250 primary school tutors working in the cuddalore education district. The aim of the study is to study the significance of the difference between the following of sub-samples with respect to their problem faced in Activity Based leering. Location of school (rural /urban), Types of school (Government / Aided) Community (OC/BC/MBC/[SC/ST]). In order to find out whether the difference between the mean Problems faced in ABL scores of primary school teachers working in Government school and Aided school is significant or not, the null hypothesis that there is no such difference and the observed difference has arisen only due to change fluctuations has been set up. The 't' value is significant at 0.05 level.

Key Words: Difficulties, ABL, Primary School & Tutors

1. Introduction:

Education in India was through the Gurukul system up to a few centuries ago till the beginning of British rule in India. During the British rule, the British brought in their education system and started schools with the aim to prepare local Indian people for jobs in the British government in India. The Indian Education System has set high constitutional goals of Universalization of Elementary Education and Education for all. The Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan, the flagship program of the Indian Government, has taken up the task of achieving universal elementary education in our country.

Educational commission reports and national debates form the basis of education reform and unfortunately educational research remains an underutilized area. Educational research is being undertaken by apex bodies of educational research such as NCERT and NUEPA or by the government itself such as the SSA and there is less of independent research in the field. Further, student achievements are studied more in terms of low levels of attainment such as ability of class V students to read class I or class II books. While it is disappointing that even at such low levels of expectations the results are so abysmal, they also allude to the fact that low expectations at all levels begets low quality at all levels. If after 93 amendments to our constitutional law, two major centralized programs and so many innovations, if India must serve its children's educational needs with high quality, the education system's reforms and innovations should be subjected to rigorous research. The evidence thus produced must serve with greater weightage as the basis for reforms in our education system. A shift in instructional methodology from traditional to any other method will be effective only if the methodology attends to certain important factors that can positively impact the education of the child and be in the best interest of the child. But in this ABL method transaction to the primary schools, tutors faced lot of problems. So the vestigator has identified the tutors working in the primary schools situated in cuddalore district as sample. Hence, the researcher has made an attempt to study the problems faced in activity based learning of the primary school tutors.

Primary School Tutors: The primary school tutors working in the school situated in Dharmapuri education district Tamil Nadu, India.

Problems Faced in Activity Based Learning: The Problems faced in Activity Based Learning of the selected sample of primary school tutors working in the schools, as revealed by the responses to the item in the problems faced in Activity Based Learning constructed and validated by K. Muruganatham (2010).

2. Objectives of the Present Study:

The following are the objectives of the study,

- To study the significance of the difference between the following of sub-samples with respect to their problem faced in Activity Based leering

- Location of School (Rural /Urban)
- Types of school (Government / Aided)
- Community (OC/BC/MBC/[SC/ST])

3. Methodology:

This study is Normative survey method has been used for the study. Difficulties faced in Activity Based Learning scale standardized by K. Muruganatham (2010) has been used to find out the Problems faced in Activity Based Learning of primary school tutors. It is taken from the school register. The tool was administered to a random sample of 250 primary school tutors working in the cuddalore education district. The scoring of the tool has been done according to the instructions given in the manual. The data has been subjected to statistical techniques like descriptive analysis and differential analysis.

4. Tool Used:

The following tool has been used for collecting data. Problems faced in Activity Based Learning scale standardized by K. Muruganatham (2010).

5. Analysis of Data:

Differential Analysis: It involves the most important procedure by which the researcher makes inferences between groups with reference to selected variables. It involves 't' test and 'F' test. A 't' test is a numerical procedures that takes into account, the size of the difference between the means of two groups the number subject in each group, and the quantum of variation of spread present in the scores. Thus the 't' test us a teaching for determining whether the performance of two groups is significantly differential or not to determine whether there are significant difference among the means of more than two groups analysis of variance referred to a ANOVA is employed. The ANOVA yields the 'F' value. 'F' value is used to find out whether there are significant difference between the means of different groups. The hypotheses are tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Table 4.1: Mean and Standard Deviation for Problems Faced in Activity Based Learning Scores

S.No	Sub-sample	Number	Mean	Standard Deviation	
1	Location of School	Rural	130	18.78	5.10
		Urban	120	17.67	4.26
2	Type of School	Government school	173	17.60	4.84
		Aided school	77	19.75	4.15
3	Community	OC	16	14.63	3.18
		BC	110	18.87	4.66
4	Religion	Hindu	178	18.11	4.78
		Muslim	13	16.69	2.86
		Christian	59	18.93	4.88
5	Total Sample	250	18.24	4.74	

It is evident from the table 4.1, that the computed mean value of the entire sample is 18.24 and S.D is 4.74. Hence it is found that the primary school tutors are facing high level of problem in ABL method.

Table 4.2: Comparison of the Means Problems Faced in ABL Scores of the Male and Female Primary School Tutors

Sub-Samples	N	Mean	SD	't' Value	Significance at 0.05 Level
Rural School	130	18.78	5.10	1.87	Not Significant
Urban School	120	17.67	4.26		
Government School	173	17.60	4.84	3.58	Significant
Aided School	77	19.75	4.15		
Other Community	16	14.63	3.18	4.66	Significant
Backward Community	110	18.87	4.66		

6. Discussions:

In order to find out whether the difference between the mean Problems faced in ABL scores of primary school teachers working in Government school and Aided school is significant or not, the null hypothesis that there is no such difference and the observed difference has arisen only due to change fluctuations has been set up. The 't' value is found to be 3.58 which is significant at 0.05 level. It is concluded that the difference between the mean Problems faced in ABL scores of primary school tutors working in Government school and Aided school is significant. The study to show that the primary school teachers working in Government school and Aided school differ significantly in their Problems faced in ABL.

It is clear from table 4.2 that 'F' ratio is found to be significant at 0.05 Level. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected as 'F' ratio is significant. The following conclusion has been reached in respect of the

hypothesis. The primary school teachers who belongs to differ in their community significantly differ in their Problems faced in ABL.

7. Findings:

The following are the important findings of the present study.

- Primary school teachers working in the school located in rural areas and urban areas do not differ significantly in their Problems faced in Activity Based Learning.
- Primary school teachers working in Government school and Aided school differ significantly in their Problems faced in Activity Based Learning.
- Primary school teachers who belongs to different community significantly different Problems faced in Activity Based Learning

8. Conclusions:

The present investigation is a unique study conducted in Tamil Nadu, one of the pioneering state in the teaching field, to study the primary school teachers problem faced in Activity Based Learning and hence this study has contributed to the field of primary education. Also the study has revealed that majority of the primary school teachers were having a average level of problem faced in Activity Based Learning and those primary school tutors can be equipped with perform in the Activity Based Learning, with the facilities available in the primary school, given by the Government of Tamil Nadu

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